

TABLE 2. ANALYSES AND μ_{eff} VALUES OF THE H₂SO COMPLEXES OF La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III) AND Gd(III)

Complexes	Analyses				μ_{eff} B.M. at 298°K
	Found %		Required %		
	N	Metal	N	Metal	
[LaC ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₂ O ₈]	3.98	20.07	4.05	20.13	—
[CeC ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₂ O ₈]	3.98	20.26	4.04	20.34	2.22
[PrC ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₂ O ₈]	3.97	20.28	4.04	20.36	3.35
[NdC ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₂ O ₈]	3.95	20.62	4.02	20.76	3.58
[SmC ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₂ O ₈]	3.89	21.34	3.97	21.43	1.58
[GdC ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₂ O ₈]	3.85	22.03	3.95	22.17	7.80

all these complexes possess 1:2 metal-ligand stoichiometry.

References

1. D. D. OZHA, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur, 1975.
2. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution". Haase, Copenhagen, 1941.
3. M. CALVIN and K. W. Wilson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003.
4. S. CHABEREK and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 5052.
5. A. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
6. D. D. OZHA, SUSHILA MEHTA, K. N. KAUL, and R. K. MEHTA, *Current Sci.*, 1974, 43, 344.

Analytical Applications of Schiff Base Copper Complexes. Gravimetric Estimation of Mg, Ca, Sr and Ba*

NARENDRA. S. RAWAT

Chemical Laboratories, Indian School of Mines, Dhanbad.

Manuscript received 6 May 1975; revised 31 July 1975; accepted 4 August 1975

MIXED metal complexes of Schiff bases of 3 formyl salicylic acid (3FSA) and ethylene diamine (en) 1, 2 diaminopropane (DAP) or 1, 2 diamino 2-methyl propane (DAMP) have been thoroughly investigated by Rawat and Phillips¹.

The complexes containing a co-ordinated copper ion associated with a second metal ion which could be an alkali metal, alkaline earth metal or a transition metal ion. A few metal complexes of Schiff bases 3FSA with en were first reported by Poddar². During the course of investigation it was observed that elements like Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba can be quantitatively precipitated by the [enLCu]Na₂, [DAPL Cu]Na₂ or [DAMPL Cu]Na₂ Complex as [enLCuX], [DAPL

Cu X], and [DAMPL Cu X] where X = Mg, Ca, Sr or Ba. In the present communication the analytical use of Schiff base metal complexes for the gravimetric determination of Mg, Ca, Sr, and Ba has been described.

[en L Cu]Na₂, R = R' = H for en
 [DAPL Cu]Na₂, R = H, R' = CH₃ for DAP
 [DAMPL Cu]Na₂, R = R' = CH₃ for DAMP

Colour of the complex is violet to blue, decomposes above 250° and magnetic moment is about 2.0 B.M. at 298°K.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. quality. 3FSA was prepared from salicylic acid and hexamine by the method of Duff and Bills³ and this was allowed to react in alcoholic solution with twice the gram mol of en, DAP or DAMP to prepare the Schiff base as suggested by Poddar⁴. The water soluble complexes of [en L Cu]Na₂, [DAPL Cu]Na₂ and [DAMPL Cu]Na₂ are the basic compounds which were used as analytical reagents. The Na₂ Cu complex of the Schiff base was obtained by mixing alcoholic solution of A.R. copper acetate to the caustic soda solution of the Schiff base. The beautiful violet colour complex obtained was quite stable in the air. It was washed with small quantity of alcohol on the goocherucible and dried in vacuo for sometime and later heated to 120° in an oven. The complexes are hydrated to different degrees but heating them first in vacuo for about 2 hr and then for about 2 hr in an oven at 120° gave water free complexes. The dry complexes were used for the quantitative estimation of Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba at about a pH of 5 to 7. The highly acidic solution leads to the formation of H₂Cu complexes.

Estimation of Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba. Mg, Ca, Sr and Ba salts contain .001M and aqueous solutions were prepared. 50 ml of this solution was taken and diluted to

*The work was carried out partly at the School of Chemistry, University of New South Wales, Australia.

NOTES

200 ml and to this 100 ml of 0.001M Na₂Cu complex solution was added. Immediate precipitation takes place. The precipitate was kept for digestion on steam bath for half an hour. The precipitate was filtered in a sintered glass crucible, washed three times with water and finally three times with alcohol. MgCu complex being soluble in alcohol was washed with ether. Finally the precipitate was dried in an oven at 100° for about 2 hr. The precipitate so obtained has the composition [en L Cu, X], [DAPL Cu, X], [DAMPL Cu, X] where X is Mg, Ca, Sr, or Ba. The results are recorded in Table I and composition of complexes is reported in another communication⁵.

out by standard methods. Carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen were analysed by the Microanalytical Laboratory of the University of New South Wales, Sydney, Australia. Copper was determined gravimetrically as [Cu en₂][Hg I₄] after destroying the ligand by sulphuric acid and nitric acid treatment. Magnesium was determined gravimetrically as Mg ammonium phosphate in the solution after removal of copper. Calcium was determined using a flame photometer.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data in Table I shows that the metal complex i.e. Na₂Cu complexes can be used for the

Table I

Estimation of Mg as [YLCu, Mg]
All weights are in mg.

Mg taken	Y = en			Y = DAP			Y = DAMP		
	Wt. of complex	Mg found	Error	Wt. of complex	Mg found	Error	Wt. of complex	Mg found	Error
25	453.0	25.03	+0.03	466.3	25.00	+0.00	482.5	25.06	+0.06
40	724.6	40.03	+0.03	747.4	40.01	+0.01	770.7	40.02	+0.02
50	905.2	50.01	+0.01	934.4	50.01	+0.01	963.0	50.00	+0.00

Estimation of Ca as [YLCu, Ca]

Ca taken	Y = en			Y = DAP			Y = DAMP		
	Wt. of complex	Ca found	Error	Wt. of complex	Ca found	Error	Wt. of complex	Ca found	Error
25	283.8	24.96	-0.04	293.6	25.05	+0.05	301.2	24.96	-0.04
40	455.1	40.03	+0.03	468.0	39.93	-0.07	483.7	40.07	+0.07
50	567.8	49.95	-0.05	586.5	50.04	+0.04	604.0	50.06	+0.06

Estimation of Sr as [YLCu, Sr]

Sr taken	Y = en			Y = DAP			Y = DAMP		
	Wt. of complex	Sr found	Error	Wt. of complex	Sr found	Error	Wt. of complex	Sr found	Error
25	144.0	25.07	+0.07	147.7	25.01	+0.01	151.8	25.8	+0.08
40	230.1	40.06	+0.06	236.3	40.02	+0.02	241.8	39.96	-0.04
50	287.5	50.03	+0.03	295.4	50.01	+0.01	303.1	50.08	+0.08

Estimation of Ba as [YLCu, Ba]

Ba taken	Y = en			Y = DAP			Y = DAMP		
	Wt. of complex	Ba found	Error	Wt. of complex	Ba found	Error	Wt. of complex	Ba found	Error
25	100.0	25.05	+0.05	103.2	24.98	-0.02	105.8	25.00	0.00
40	160.8	39.92	-0.08	165.1	39.97	-0.03	169.2	39.99	-0.01
50	201.3	49.96	-0.04	206.4	49.96	-0.04	211.3	49.92	-0.08

Analysis of the complex. The analysis of the metal ion Cu, Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba in the complex was carried gravimetric estimation of magnesium, calcium, strontium and barium. Solutions containing as

little as 10 mg. can be determined by this method. Common anions like chloride, bromide, nitrate, etc. do not interfere in the determination of the violet colour complexes [Y L Cu, Mg], [Y L Cu, Ca], [Y L Cu, Sr] and [Y L Cu, Ba] are still stable upto 250°, above this temperature they start decomposing. Only the MgCu complexes are soluble in methyl alcohol. The remaining are insoluble in water, acetone, alcohol, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, ether, benzene and pyridine.

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to the University Grants Commission for awarding him the Colombo Plan Fellowship to attend the UNESCO course on Research Techniques in Chemistry at the School of Chemistry, University of New South Wales, Australia, where most of this work was carried out.

References

1. N. S. RAWAT and D. J. PHILLIPS, *Austr. J. Chem.* (Communicated).
2. S. N. PODDAR, *Zeitschrift für anorg. und allgemeine Chemie*, 1963, **322**, 326.
3. J. DUFF and E. BILLS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 1987.
4. S. N. PODDAR, *loc. cit.*, 1963, **322**, 328.
5. N. S. RAWAT, *Indian J. Chem.* (accepted for publication).

Spectrophotometric studies of Cu(II) complexes with Schiff Bases

PRABUDDHA JAIN AND KAMAL, K. CHATURVEDI

Department of Chemistry, Holkar Science College, Indore.

Manuscript received 21 May 1975, accepted 21 August 1975

THE complexes of copper with sulphamethazine salicylaldimine (SUMTSA), sulphadiazinesalicylaldimine (SUDSA) and sulphamerazine salicylaldimine (SUMRSA) have been studied spectrophotometrically at 20°. Cu(II) forms 1:2 complexes with these ligands. Stability constants are determined by applying Job's method and Raghavrao's method. Free energy values have also been evaluated.

The synthesis and analysis of ligands have been described in previous communications^{1,2,3}.

A Beckman model Du spectrophotometer was used for absorption measurements. The studies were carried out in acetone/alcohol (1:1 by vol.) mixture.

The max. for copper acetate was found at 765nm., that of Cu-SUDSA complex at 330nm. (pH7.0) of Cu-SUMTSA complex at 395nm. (pH7.0) and of Cu-SUMRSA complex at 340nm (pH7.0). These wavelengths were chosen for the study of stoichiometry of the components by Job's method of continuous variation using equimolar solutions. The validity of Beer's law was seen. The absorbance measurements were carried out after 24 hr of equilibration. The colour did not fade even after a week. The pH of the solution were adjusted at required level by using different buffer solutions.

The stability constants were calculated from absorbance data (a) by extrapolation of Job's curve

obtained by using equimolar solutions as suggested by Raghavarao⁴, (b) using Job's method of nonequimolar solutions as modified by Foley-Anderson⁵ and Dey⁶.

The values of stability constants and free energy changes are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I. STABILITY CONSTANTS

S. No.	Complex	Method A		Method B	
		log K	$\frac{\Delta G}{K \text{ cal/mole}}$	log K	$\frac{\Delta G}{K \text{ cal/mole}}$
1	Cu-SUMTSA	9.08	-11.35	10.04	-12.55
2.	Cu-SUDSA	9.65	-12.06	10.52	-13.15
3.	Cu-SUMRSA	9.03	-11.29	10.40	-13.00

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of a junior research fellowship to one of them (P.J.).

References

1. P. JAIN, KAMAL K. CHATURVEDI and R. KAUSHAL, *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, (Communicated).
2. P. JAIN, K. K. CHATURVEDI and R. KAUSHAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, (Communicated).
3. P. JAIN, K. K. CHATURVEDI and R. KAUSHAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* (Communicated).
4. K. V. SUBBARAMARAO and H. S. V. RAGHAVARAO, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, **14B**, 278.
5. R. T. FOLEY and R. C. ANDERSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1195; 1949, **71**, 909.
6. A. K. DEY and coworkers, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1958, **6**, 314; *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1958, **18**, 324.

The Effect of Bubble Formation on Hydrogen Overpotential at Mercury Cathodes

F. R. SMITH

Chemistry Department, Memorial University,
St. John's, Nfld, Canada.

and

S. N. DAS*

Chemistry Department Science College, Patna 800005

Manuscript received 23 May 1975, revised 17 July 1975,
accepted 17 July 1975

BUBBLE overvoltages¹ were traditionally recorded to indicate the "minimum" overvoltage for electrolytic gas evolution reactions. Contemporary electrode kinetics² pays no heed to such subjective observations, which appear to have no fundamental significance. We wish to report a new effect, that of bubble formation on hydrogen overpotential measurements at high purity (5X distilled) mercury.

A centro-symmetric cell was used, with connecting tubes to the anode and reference hydrogen electrodes directly above the mercury cup. Hydrochloric acid

*For correspondence